

D5.2 Participatory Scenario Development Report

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CoP	Community of Practice
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
PROJECT PARTNERS	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN'S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HÖGSKOLAN FOR LÄRANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JÖNKÖPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

1. INTRODUCTION

FLIARA Work Package 2 implemented envisioning, innovation and assessment processes to come up with a number of measures to promote women’s contributions to sustainability innovations in agriculture and rural domains. During the distillation process, for example, 20 vision cards were developed to illustrate innovations that have potential to address common agricultural and rural sustainability problems (Figure 1, separate cards are available in Annex 1).

Figure 1. FLIARA Innovations Cards.

The participatory distillation process produced also 18 measures that were considered most promising in promoting women-led sustainability innovations (Figure 2). Taking a closer look, about 80% of these measures were social in character (e.g. co-operation and visibility platforms as well as empowerment) and only 20% were ‘traditional’ measures (e.g. finance, subsidies, simplification of bureaucracy). This calls for a major re-orientation of agricultural and rural innovation policies.

Figure 2. Most promising measures to promote women’s contributions to agricultural and rural sustainability innovations. Source: D2.4.

Even if the single measures may enhance women’s potential to innovate and address multidimensional sustainability problems, the finding could be further elaborated toward more extensive policies. These broader policies could upgrade the single measures to a new systems level and policy paradigm level that have a higher impact potential than separate measures. This report details how this was done in the FLIARA project.

1.1 OBJECTIVE

One of the objectives of WP5 (Policy Design and Assessment) was to ‘engage stakeholders in a process of participatory scenario development to imagine potential future contexts and their impacts and outcomes for policy, identify options to adapt policy and governance structures for future change’.

Further on, the task was to (emphasis added):

‘Conduct a series of focus groups with key stakeholders, namely women leading farming and rural innovations, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders in a process of Participatory Scenario Development. The qualitative and participatory techniques applied in a Participatory Scenario Development exercise encourage discussion, deliberation, and the exchange of thoughts. The process also provides a **framework to support future decisions and stimulate engagement in the process of change.**’

So, the process implemented in association within the four Communities of Practice (CoP) events was aiming at developing the separate promising measures identified in WP2 into broader policy paradigms, approaches or programmes to have a wider impact. This process is described next.

2. METHODOLOGY

FLIARA project organised four CoPs in Ireland, Italy, Slovenia and Sweden. In each of the meetings, the participants were divided into two groups: ‘newcomers’ and ‘oldies’. The ‘newcomers’ participated in the CoP for the first time whereas ‘oldies’ had participated before.

Vision workshops

The ‘newcomers’ participated in a Vision Workshop. They were divided into groups of 5–7 people with mixed backgrounds. The task of each group was to pick up a vision card (out of the twenty cards presented in Figure 1 and described more in detail in D2.2) representing **a vision in which women could make an important contribution** – based on their assessment within the context where the CoP was organised. After the discussion and selection, each group proposed measures that would be needed to realise the vision. After this round, a second vision card was selected and furnished with measures in the same way. These processes, organised in each of the four CoPs in the same way, resulted in a set of most promising visions, observing the diverse contexts across Europe.

Altogether, 232 members of the research and innovation consortium, FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors as well as local experts and stakeholders contributed to the outcome. The numbers are given in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Contexts of the Vision Workshops and the number of participants.

CoP context	Participants
Ireland (Galway)	80
Slovenia (Ljubljana)	70
Italy (Cosenza)	45
Sweden (Växjö)	37
Total	232

Scenario workshops

After each CoP and ‘newcomer’ workshop, the most promising visions were selected for further processing in the next CoP by participants (‘oldies’) who were already done with the ‘newcomer’ workshop. Their task was to **create a storyline for the future and explain why the vision in question had become realised**. The participants were again divided into groups of 5–7 people with mixed backgrounds. Three most popular cards from the previous CoP were elaborated toward primitive scenarios. Each card/group was supported with a summary of the proposals of the ‘newcomer’ workshop that had elaborated the vision. Each group was suggested to use some of the ingredients proposed by the Vision Card workshop but was still free to add some new ingredients. Examples of the output of the ‘newcomer’ workshops are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Examples of summaries of the Vision Workshop outputs to feed the Scenario Workshops.

A total of 80 members of the research and innovation consortium, FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors and local stakeholders contributed to the outcome. The numbers are given in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Contexts of the Scenario Workshops and the number of participants.

CoP context	Participants
Ireland (Galway)	–
Slovenia (Ljubljana)	18
Italy (Cosenza)	30
Sweden (Växjö)	32
Total	80

The next step included consolidation of the policy scenarios. The target was to create a limited number of backcasting scenarios (Dreborg 1996) that connect the broad FLIARA vision to the present through alternative pathways. Whereas the forecasting scenarios may suffer from the risk of ‘extending the present’ (Slaughter 1993, 294), the backcasting scenarios as manifestation of alternative futures break the direct link to the present

because they start from the normative future vision rather than from the present. This is crucial in trying to reach understanding about alternative future possibilities that are truly different from the current realities. At this stage, the outputs of the scenario workshops were enriched by the outputs of other WPs.

Backcasting scenarios (Robinson 2003, 839, 842):

In response to the problem of prediction, backcasting adopts a scenario analysis approach. In response to the problem of desirability, it consists of an explicitly normative form of scenario analysis. As a result, the major distinguishing characteristic of backcasting is a concern with how desirable futures can be attained. FLIARA_report D52. It involves working backwards from a particular desired future end-point or set of goals to the present, in order to determine the physical feasibility of that future and the policy measures that would be required to reach that point ...desired future is not determined in advance of the analysis but is an emergent property of the process of engaging with users and project partners. In this sense backcasting contributes to a process of social learning about possible and desirable futures.

The final stage took the form of a **synthesis workshop** following all CoPs. Five key experts of Galway and UTU teams participated in a two-day internal workshop targeted to translate and synthesise all the ingredients into a handful of scenarios that have a capacity to make us aware of future alternatives and serve choices in the present (Slaughter 1993). A feasible number of future alternatives that can serve choices in the present is 'about a handful' rather than, say, 5,000 detailed futures (Kuhmonen 2025). The process was highly iterative, and much of the materials that were produced in the previous stages were incorporated to the final outcome. A systematic consistency check was carried out to ensure this demand. The final outcome consisted of eight backcasting policy scenarios that will be described and discussed later in this report.

Finally, the scenarios were tested for their feasibility and impact potential in the General Assembly of the research and innovation consortium in Brussels (October 2025). In this **assessment workshop**, the 18 participants were split into eight groups and each of the group assessed one policy scenario. Each of the scenarios was assessed along three dimensions: preferability (not preferred at all 1 – very much preferred 10), possibility (not possible at all 1 – very much possible 10) and probability (not probable at all 1 – very much probable 10). As the participants of the assessment workshop were experts (consortium members) who had been working with women-led innovations in the FLIARA project for three years, the assessment results were robust. Main steps of the process are described in Figure 4 and Figure 5 which includes also the preceding steps in WP2. Overall, the process resembles distillation process where subsequent stages leave less and less material that is higher and higher quality.

Figure 4. Main steps of the policy scenario development.

Figure 5. Connection of policy scenario development and foresight Work Package (WP2).

3. RESULTS

Vision Workshops

Each group in the vision workshops discussed and selected two visions in which women could make an important contribution to sustainability innovations in each specific context. The results of this selection process are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of the selection process in Vision Workshops.

# Innovation card	Galway votes	Ljubljana votes	Cosenza votes	Växjö votes	Joker points	Total
12 Rural image	5	0	1	1	2	9
13 Local food	1	4	0	0	1	6
2 Sustainable lifestyles	1	2	0	1	1	5
15 Funding models	3	0	1	0	0	4
3 Community	1	0	1	1	1	4
5 Products and services	1	1	1	0	1	4
14 Policy-making	1	1	1	0	1	4
17 Human welfare	0	1	1	1	0	3
20 Gender roles	2	0	0	1	0	3
4 Sustainable farming	0	0	0	2	1	3
7 New technology	2	0	0	0	0	2
19 New competences	0	0	2	0	0	2
1 Local development	0	1	0	0	1	2
6 Concerted action	0	0	1	0	0	1
10 Rural livelihoods	1	0	0	0	0	1
16 Heritage	1	0	0	0	0	1
18 Nature conservation	0	0	0	0	1	1
8 Renewable energy	0	0	0	0	0	0
9 Housing possibilities	0	0	0	0	0	0
11 Local services	0	0	0	0	0	0

The most popular or promising visions were related to rural image, local food, sustainable lifestyles, funding models, communality, products and services as well as policy making (for the vision cards, see Annex 1). These seven visions covered two thirds of the selected vision cards. The popularity of specific visions did not follow any regional pattern except for rural image that was popular in the north-west and local food that was popular in the south. Each of the visions address specific rural and agricultural sustainability problems, as for example renewal of ‘rural image’ would address lack of economic diversification, lack of sustainability wisdom and selective population decline.

Annex 2 reports the outputs of the vision workshop. The results can be used as an inspirational material for policy and project design. They also indicate diversity of the manifestations of visions.

The visions that were most popular in each vision workshop were further developed into primitive scenario cards that could serve the subsequent scenario workshops. The cards were based on conventional content analysis (without predefined categories; Hsieh and Shannon 2005) of the vision workshop output. Through this analysis the cards synthesise

the output and capture most relevant elements detailed in Annex 2. These cards are presented in Annex 3.

Scenario workshops

Each group of the scenario workshops discussed one card or primitive scenario and tried to create a storyline around the elements as well as enrich the elements based on the storyline logics. Output of the scenario workshops is presented in Annex 4.

All the previous steps served creation of policy scenarios that could serve policy design and policy choices. In the final synthesis workshop, most of the elements proposed in the vision cards and scenario workshops were included in eight scenarios (Figure 6).

Figure 6. FLIARA backcasting policy scenarios.

Each of the scenarios creates a bridge between the generic FLIARA vision (more women-led farm-based and rural multidimensional sustainability innovations that address sustainability problems) and the present. Each of the policy scenarios has also a more specific contribution to the normative vision.

In order to be useful, the (policy) scenario descriptions tend to be quite short even if their distillation has been a long and rich process. This was the case also here. Each scenario includes three parts: problems and drivers, policies and pathways as well as outcomes. **Problems and drivers** in the present provide a motivation to choose a specific scenario as a starting point of policy or project design in a specific context. **Policies and pathways** illustrate some of the most promising measures that are needed to connect the vision with the present. **Outcomes** manifest the specific contribution of the scenario to the generic FLIARA vision.

Two versions of the scenarios were created: a short ‘card version’ that can be used e.g. in workshops as printed versions and a bit more extensive ‘page versions’ that are more detailed and nuanced. The ‘card versions’ of the scenarios are provided in Figures 7–14 and the ‘page versions’ in Annex 5.

1 Valued and Visible: Empowering Rural and Farm Women as Change Makers

Problems and drivers: Rural areas face declining social capital, economic stagnation and entrenched behaviours, but empowering and connecting rural women can break these cycles and promote sustainable, future-oriented development.

Policies and pathways: Capacity-building, visibility platforms and targeted incentives are key to supporting female change-makers, requiring holistic and inclusive policies that address social, economic, environmental and cultural dimensions.

Outcomes: Empowered and recognised women foster innovation, sustainability and resilience in rural areas, strengthening future investments and community engagement.

Figure 7. FLIARA policy scenario 1: Valued and visible: Empowering rural and farm women as change makers.

2

Diversified Rural Images beyond Agriculture and Traditional Norms

Problems and drivers: Rural areas face economic stagnation, outmigration of young and educated people—especially women—and persistent stereotypes as well as rigid traditions that hinder innovation and sustainability.

Policies and pathways: Positive change relies on making rural opportunities visible through collaboration with creative industries, education reforms, empowerment of key enablers and place-based policies that value local strengths and diversity.

Outcomes: Modernised mindsets and renewed rural identities have increased diversity, pride and attractiveness of rural areas, drawing more young, educated people and women back into rural life and agriculture.

Figure 8. FLIARA policy scenario 2: Diversified rural images beyond agriculture and traditional norms.

3

Sustainable Agriculture: A Positive and Empowering Choice for Women

Problems and drivers: Rural areas face declining social capital, economic downturn and lack of faith in the future that hinder progress, but empowering and connecting rural women can catalyse sustainable and inclusive transformation.

Policies and pathways: Capacity building, visibility initiatives and targeted incentives for women—supported by holistic, anti-discriminatory policies—are essential to foster innovation and multidimensional sustainability.

Outcomes: Empowered and visible women drive transformative sustainability efforts, strengthen community resilience and inspire renewed investment and optimism in rural and agricultural futures.

Figure 9. FLIARA policy scenario 3: Sustainable agriculture: A positive and empowering choice for women.

4

From Margins to Mainstream: Women at the Heart of Sustainable Rural Economies

Problems and drivers: Rural economies, heavily reliant on specialised agriculture and lacking diversification, face infrastructure deficits, poor public transport and selective population decline, leading to the marginalization of local cultures and traditions.

Policies and pathways: Localised, small-scale approaches that empower women through tailored support, micro-funding and autonomy foster community-driven innovations and improve rural services and infrastructure.

Outcomes: Expanded employment opportunities and female-led innovations have diversified rural economies, revitalised communities and strengthened their economic and social resilience.

Figure 10. FLIARA policy scenario 4: From margins to mainstream: Women at the heart of sustainable rural economies.

5

Support for Women as Promoters of Sustainable rural Communities

Problems and drivers: Rural communities struggle with low social capital, population decline, housing shortages, cultural marginalisation and weak youth engagement, all of which limit women’s ability to build sustainable lives in these areas.

Policies and pathways: Place-based, bottom-up approaches that empower self-organised local systems—driven by women and supported by social innovations—foster community resilience, inclusion and renewal.

Outcomes: Strengthened social capital and local pride have revitalised rural areas, with women, youth and newcomers driving social innovation and transforming communities into vibrant, sustainable places to live.

Figure 11. FLIARA policy scenario 5: Support for women as promoters of sustainable rural communities.

6

Inclusion and Representation of Agriculture and Rural Women in Networks and Decision-making Forums

Problems and drivers: Women remain underrepresented in networks and decision-making forums, limiting perspectives on sustainability and inclusion and reinforcing cycles of disengagement and underrepresentation.

Policies and pathways: A combined approach of legal ('hard') measures—such as equality laws and quotas—and cultural ('soft') measures promoting inclusivity and visibility helps institutionalise gender equality and shift societal mindsets.

Outcomes: Greater female participation in decision-making strengthens social capital, enhances innovation and advances multidimensional sustainability in rural and agricultural sectors.

Figure 12. FLIARA policy scenario 6: Inclusion and representation of agriculture and rural women in networks and decision-making forums.

7

Development and Adoption of New Technologies to Improve Farm and Rural Women's Work Life Opportunities

Problems and drivers: Many rural areas lack modern, accessible technologies, limiting productivity, increasing workload and discouraging women—especially younger ones—from pursuing farming or rural livelihoods, leading to population decline and weakened social capital.

Policies and pathways: Gender-sensitive technology development, combined with targeted training through Local Action Groups, Fab Labs and Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), ensures women can access, adopt and benefit from new tools and practices.

Outcomes: Improved access to and training in technology have enhanced productivity, work-life balance and the attractiveness of farming and rural employment for women, revitalising rural communities.

Figure 13. FLIARA policy scenario 7: Development and adoption of new technologies to improve farm and rural women's work life opportunities.

8

Accessible and Flexible Funding and Support Models that Enable Diverse Women-led Innovation Journeys in Farms and Rural Areas

Problems and drivers: Many existing policies are overly bureaucratic, inefficient and poorly aligned with women’s needs, contributing to low diversification and weak social capital in rural and farming communities.

Policies and pathways: Flexible, vision-based funding models, community-driven financing and targeted support structures—such as mentorships, innovation hubs and pilot projects—enable women to start, scale and sustain rural enterprises.

Outcomes: Gender-responsive and locally adapted policies have diversified rural economies, strengthened sustainability and enhanced the resilience of farming and rural communities.

Figure 14. FLIARA policy scenario 8: Accessible and flexible funding and support models that enable diverse women-led innovation journeys in farms and rural areas.

The policy scenarios were assessed for their coverage and feasibility in several steps. During the long logical distillation process they were ultimately meant to resolve rural and agricultural sustainability problems, which was the starting point of the whole foresight process (see Figure 5 and WP2 deliverables).

To ensure this, each policy scenario was contrasted against the original most common sustainability problems. Figure 15 reports the results of this **coverage analysis**. As

evident, all most common sustainability problems were included in several scenarios as one of their outcomes, if they were implemented.

MOST COMMON RURAL SUSTAINABILITY PROBLEMS	COVERED BY POLICY SCENARIO							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Lack of infrastructure, facilities, local services, amenities and activities				●		●		
Lack of social capital, cohesion and communality	●				●	●	●	●
Inefficient, distant and/or bureaucratic policies			●				●	
Selective population decline (e.g. young, women, educated)		●		●	●	●		●
Lack of economic diversification, restructuring and jobs		●	●	●		●	●	
Inequality: gender, social and/or regional				●	●			
Urban and/or growth bias in sustainability discourses and solutions		●		●				
Limited availability of feasible accommodation (houses, prices)								●
Marginalisation of local culture and traditions				●				●
Problematic business environment, especially for small farms/firms			●	●		●		
Unsustainable land management practices			●					
Lock-in and path dependence in thought and action	●	●						
Lack of public transport, use of cars				●				
Passivity, lack of involvement	●				●			●
Lack of sustainability wisdom		●			●			
Lack of young farmers and successions			●			●		
Dual impact of environmental regulations (conservation/restriction)			●					
Weak advocacy and involvement of young people								●
Environmental damage caused by agriculture			●					
Limited availability of land (e.g. urbanisation)			●					
Water management problems (scarcity, droughts, floods, erosion)			●					
Poor marketing of the opportunities and the area		●						
Alienation of people from food production			●					
Mixed expectations and policy incentives for farming			●					
Harmful consumption patterns	●							
High living costs								●
Ignorance for aesthetic aspects								●

Figure 15. Coverage of the policy scenarios in terms of rural and agricultural sustainability problems they could address.

Another topic to be covered by the scenarios were the most promising measures to promote women’s contributions to rural and agricultural sustainability innovations that resolve the problems. This analysis indicates that the eight scenarios have a good coverage of these promising measures (Figure 16).

MOST EFFECTIVE MEASURES TO PROMOTE WOMEN'S CONTRIBUTIONS TO SUSTAINABILITY INNOVATIONS	COVERED BY POLICY SCENARIO							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Organisation of platforms for co-creation and cooperation				●		●	●	
Provision of information about alternatives, examples and good practices		●	●			●		
Provision of education	●	●	●			●		
Adoption of equality of genders and social groups in all roles and activities	●		●		●	●		
Promotion of vision-based and goal-oriented actions and policies			●				●	
Provision of adequate local services and facilities including internet connection				●				●
Empowerment and encouragement to innovate	●	●	●	●		●	●	●
Provision of incentives and support for entrepreneurship			●	●		●	●	
Adoption of place-based policies		●		●		●	●	●
Provision of finance and subsidies			●	●		●	●	
Organisation of platforms to provide visibility for innovative persons and their insights	●				●			
Strengthening of support networks to allow involvement						●		●
Genuine involvement of young people to have an impact			●					●
Provision of communal spaces						●		●
Promotion of flexible work life						●		
Promotion of innovations by means of projects	●					●		
Simplification of bureaucracy and regulation			●					
Adoption of welcoming policies and openness					●			●

Figure 16. Coverage of the policy scenarios in terms of most promising measures to promote women's contributions to rural and agricultural sustainability innovations.

Further on, the proposed policy scenarios were assessed in terms of their feasibility: possibility, preferability and probability to have an expected impact. The results of this analysis are presented in Figures 17–20. The results indicate that preferability of the scenarios tends to be much higher than the probability of their realisation and application. Overall, highest ratings for the three qualities were given to Scenario 4 (From margins to mainstream: Women at the heart of sustainable rural economies), Scenario 7 (Development and adoption of new technologies to improve farm and rural women's work life opportunities) and Scenario 6 (Inclusion of agriculture and rural women in networks and decision-making forums).

A change in the mindsets and worldviews is the elements that is in highest demand to have more policies to promote women-led sustainability innovations in rural and agricultural domains.

The scenarios in various forms can be utilised in policy design and in raising awareness of the needs for change of the dominant mindsets.

1

Valued and Visible: Empowering Rural and Farm Women as Change Makers

Problems and drivers: Rural areas face declining social capital, economic stagnation and entrenched behaviours, but empowering and connecting rural women can break these cycles and promote sustainable, future-oriented development.

Policies and pathways: Capacity-building, visibility platforms and targeted incentives are key to supporting female change-makers, requiring holistic and inclusive policies that address social, economic, environmental and cultural dimensions.

Outcomes: Empowered and recognised women foster innovation, sustainability and resilience in rural areas, strengthening future investments and community engagement.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 9.5/10 ★★☆☆
- Possibility 7.5/10 ★★☆☆
- Probability 6.0/10 ★☆☆☆

COMMENTS:

- Change is needed, but overall, not just women
- Cluster change agents
- Focus on quality: formal, informal, institutional
- Perhaps notify: social entrepreneurship

2

Diversified Rural Images beyond Agriculture and Traditional Norms

Problems and drivers: Rural areas face economic stagnation, outmigration of young and educated people—especially women—and persistent stereotypes as well as rigid traditions that hinder innovation and sustainability.

Policies and pathways: Positive change relies on making rural opportunities visible through collaboration with creative industries, education reforms, empowerment of key enablers and place-based policies that value local strengths and diversity.

Outcomes: Modernised mindsets and renewed rural identities have increased diversity, pride and attractiveness of rural areas, drawing more young, educated people and women back into rural life and agriculture.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability ../10
- Possibility ../10
- Probability ../10

COMMENTS:

- Many regions need to concentrate again to traditional identity factors
- New image may not attract youth but jobs, public transport and care services
- Titles may be misleading for some people
- New image is needed, but it is only one element rather than gamechanger
- Economic and income opportunities are the key
- Economic diversification can be also a problem, if you lose image and identify features
- Sustainability framing might affect on the image of agriculture in many ways
- Positive agricultural realities remain a bit illusive

Figure 17. Assessment results of the FLIARA policy scenarios, part 1.

3

Sustainable Agriculture: A Positive and Empowering Choice for Women

Problems and drivers: Rural areas face declining social capital, economic downturn and lack of faith in the future that hinder progress, but empowering and connecting rural women can catalyse sustainable and inclusive transformation.

Policies and pathways: Capacity building, visibility initiatives and targeted incentives for women—supported by holistic, anti-discriminatory policies—are essential to foster innovation and multidimensional sustainability.

Outcomes: Empowered and visible women drive transformative sustainability efforts, strengthen community resilience and inspire renewed investment and optimism in rural and agricultural futures.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 9.3/10 ★★★★★
- Possibility 7.3/10 ★★★
- Probability 6.0/10 ★

COMMENTS:

- Note: home gardens could be an entry point to agriculture profession
- Most of all women enterprises are practising sustainable agriculture but we need change in policies to make it possible and probable
- Preferred but changing this need time
- Counter-discourse: yes, but can be then produce enough food for citizens and the hungry world
- Ensuring sufficient food production and sufficient number of farmers is critical

4

From Margins to Mainstream: Women at the Heart of Sustainable Rural Economies

Problems and drivers: Rural economies, heavily reliant on specialised agriculture and lacking diversification, face infrastructure deficits, poor public transport and selective population decline, leading to the marginalization of local cultures and traditions.

Policies and pathways: Localised, small-scale approaches that empower women through tailored support, micro-funding and autonomy foster community-driven innovations and improve rural services and infrastructure.

Outcomes: Expanded employment opportunities and female-led innovations have diversified rural economies, revitalised communities and strengthened their economic and social resilience.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 8.5/10 ★★★★★
- Possibility 9.0/10 ★★★★★
- Probability 8.5/10 ★★★★★

COMMENTS:

- Public services respond to community needs and this attracts population, jobs, innovation and add to wellbeing and communality
- Caregiving work relies heavily on women, granting more support can increase this without dealing with gender roles
- Resilient yes if comprehensive policies enable them to flourish (e.g. change in regulations to SME reporting, criteria for funding)

Figure 18. Assessment results of the FLIARA policy scenarios, part 2.

5

Support for Women as Promoters of Sustainable rural Communities

Problems and drivers: Rural communities struggle with low social capital, population decline, housing shortages, cultural marginalisation and weak youth engagement, all of which limit women's ability to build sustainable lives in these areas.

Policies and pathways: Place-based, bottom-up approaches that empower self-organised local systems—driven by women and supported by social innovations—foster community resilience, inclusion and renewal.

Outcomes: Strengthened social capital and local pride have revitalised rural areas, with women, youth and newcomers driving social innovation and transforming communities into vibrant, sustainable places to live.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 6.5/10 ★
- Possibility 7.5/10 ★★
- Probability 7.0/10 ★★

COMMENTS:

- This scenario could create more work and burdens for the women in a context in which reproductive work is already undervalued and unequally distributed
- Increasing rural pride is important to reproduce local culture and heritage
- The language could be quite difficult for local actors and policy makers
- Encouraging self-organising systems could also have drawbacks for women instead of getting proper support from the government agencies and financial resources

6

Inclusion and Representation of Agriculture and Rural Women in Networks and Decision-making Forums

Problems and drivers: Women remain underrepresented in networks and decision-making forums, limiting perspectives on sustainability and inclusion and reinforcing cycles of disengagement and underrepresentation.

Policies and pathways: A combined approach of legal ('hard') measures—such as equality laws and quotas—and cultural ('soft') measures promoting inclusivity and visibility helps institutionalise gender equality and shift societal mindsets.

Outcomes: Greater female participation in decision-making strengthens social capital, enhances innovation and advances multidimensional sustainability in rural and agricultural sectors.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 9.0/10 ★★★★★
- Possibility 9.0/10 ★★★★★
- Probability 8.0/10 ★★★

COMMENTS:

- Higher probability asks for a broader change of norms and values that need to be aligned with the core spirit of the laws and legislations so that the laws are supported and applied at a deeper level in organisation dynamics – let people hear and discuss persisting barriers and discrimination rural women are facing
- Laws alone do not change mindsets: there is a need for support actions

Figure 19. Assessment results of the FLIARA policy scenarios, part 3.

7

Development and Adoption of New Technologies to Improve Farm and Rural Women's Work Life Opportunities

Problems and drivers: Many rural areas lack modern, accessible technologies, limiting productivity, increasing workload and discouraging women—especially younger ones—from pursuing farming or rural livelihoods, leading to population decline and weakened social capital.

Policies and pathways: Gender-sensitive technology development, combined with targeted training through Local Action Groups, Fab Labs and Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), ensures women can access, adopt and benefit from new tools and practices.

Outcomes: Improved access to and training in technology have enhanced productivity, work-life balance and the attractiveness of farming and rural employment for women, revitalising rural communities.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 9.5/10 ★★★★★
- Possibility 8.5/10 ★★★★★
- Probability 9.5/10 ★★★★★

COMMENTS:

- Improved digital options increase possibilities in working in rural areas and home
- New 'urban' jobs can't replace traditional farming and rural jobs, however
- Risk: digitalisation will happen only close to urban and tourism centers
- Investing and mentoring support is needed
- The broadband problem still exists
- Centralised funding and support still remains as a problem for many rural areas

8

Accessible and Flexible Funding and Support Models that Enable Diverse Women-led Innovation Journeys in Farms and Rural Areas

Problems and drivers: Many existing policies are overly bureaucratic, inefficient and poorly aligned with women's needs, contributing to low diversification and weak social capital in rural and farming communities.

Policies and pathways: Flexible, vision-based funding models, community-driven financing and targeted support structures—such as mentorships, innovation hubs and pilot projects—enable women to start, scale and sustain rural enterprises.

Outcomes: Gender-responsive and locally adapted policies have diversified rural economies, strengthened sustainability and enhanced the resilience of farming and rural communities.

RATING (average of all votes):

- Preferability 10.0/10 ★★★★★
- Possibility 9.0/10 ★★★★★
- Probability 4.3/10 ★★☆☆☆

COMMENTS:

- Pilot studies and benchmarking could assist in getting political support
- Investments in local and regional networks and social enterprises are also important
- Funding needs visibility
- Funding through local actors is important as well as more organisation structures at local levels (e.g. integrated partnerships)
- Check best practices from tech startups
- Lessons from urban incubation spaces and private/corporate finance support
- This vision can be transformative for wider funding system also

Figure 20. Assessment results of the FLIARA policy scenarios, part 4.

REFERENCES

- Dreborg, K. H. 1996. Essence of backcasting. *Futures* 28 (9), 813–828.
- Hsieh, H.-F. & Shannon, S.E. 2005. Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative Health Research* 15 (9), 1277–1288.
- Kuhmonen, T. 2025. Design principles for alternative futures of Complex Adaptive Systems. Academic dissertation. FFRC publications 1/2025. Finland Futures Research Centre, University of Turku.
- Robinson, J. 2003. Futures subjunctive: backcasting as social learning. *Futures* 35, 839–856.
- Slaughter, R. A. 1993. Futures concepts. *Futures* 25 (3), 289–314.

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Vision cards.

●●●● VISION CARD ●●●●

1

LOCAL DEVELOPMENT

Local development has been organised in a new way to address the following sustainability problems:

- Lack of economic diversification
- Lack of infrastructure and facilities
- Selective population decline

SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES

Sustainable lifestyles and practices have been adopted to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of sustainability wisdom**
- **Lack of infrastructure and facilities**
- **Lack of public transport**

COMMUNALITY

Communality and involvement of people have been organised in novel ways to address the following sustainability problems:

- Lack of social capital
- Selective population decline
- Lack of economic diversification

SUSTAINABLE FARMING

Sustainable farming models have become mainstream to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Alienation from food production**
- **Water management problems**
- **Lack of young farmers and successions**

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

Novel products, services and business models have been developed to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of public transport**
- **Lack of economic diversification**
- **Lack of infrastructure and facilities**

CONCERTED ACTION

Concerted action has been organised successfully to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of economic diversification**
- **Lack of sustainability wisdom**
- **Inefficient, distant and/or bureaucratic policies**

NEW TECHNOLOGY

New technology has been utilised e.g. in communication to address the following sustainability problems:

- Lack of infrastructure and facilities
- Lack of social capital
- Selective population decline

RENEWABLE ENERGY

Renewable energy facilities and communities have been set up to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of sustainability wisdom**
- **Lack of infrastructure and facilities**
- **Unsustainable land management practices**

HOUSING POSSIBILITIES

Attractive housing possibilities are made available to address the following sustainability problems:

- Limited availability of accommodation
- Lack of social capital
- Selective population decline

RURAL LIVELIHOODS

Rural livelihoods and jobs are made accessible to address the following sustainability problems:

- Lack of infrastructure and facilities
- Selective population decline
- Marginalisation of local culture and traditions

LOCAL SERVICES

Local services have been reorganised and preserved to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of infrastructure and facilities**
- **Lack of social capital**
- **Lack of public transport**

RURAL IMAGE

Rural image has been renewed to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of economic diversification**
- **Lack of sustainability wisdom**
- **Selective population decline**

LOCAL FOOD

Local food and short food chains have become mainstream to address the following sustainability problems:

- Alienation from food production
- Lack of infrastructure and facilities
- Environmentage damage caused by agriculture

POLICY-MAKING

Policy-making has become fact-based to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of public transport**
- **Lack of sustainability wisdom**
- **Lack of involvement**

FUNDING MODELS

Novel funding models have been adopted to address the following sustainability problems:

- Inefficient, distant and/or bureaucratic policies
- Lack of economic diversification
- Lack of social capital

HERITAGE

Heritage has been preserved to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of social capital**
- **Lack of sustainability wisdom**
- **Unsustainable land management practices**

HUMAN WELFARE

Human welfare has been promoted in new ways to address the following sustainability problems:

- Lack of social capital
- Selective population decline
- Poor marketing of the opportunities of the area

NATURE CONSERVATION

Nature conservation has been promoted to address the following sustainability problems:

- Lack of infrastructure and facilities
- Unsustainable land and water management practices
- Ignorance for aesthetic aspects

NEW COMPETENCES

Reform of educational curricula has provided people with new competences to address the following sustainability problems:

- Selective population decline
- Lack of sustainability wisdom
- Weak advocacy and involvement of young people

GENDER ROLES

Gender roles have been reformed to address the following sustainability problems:

- **Lack of social capital**
- **Passivity, lack of involvement**
- **Lock-in and path dependence in thought and action**

Annex 2. Output of the vision card workshops ('newcomers').

1 Local development	2 Sustainable lifestyles	3 Communitarity
Needs to come from the community	The need for people 'in office' to have passion and drive	looking where the gaps are (Recruitment in social services)
When demand comes up, support and ideas need to be offered	Promoting best practice	helping to reconnect farming and non-farming communities, - interconnection to related other sectors (pollination to farm..),
Local development + sustainable lifestyles = local services, housing, communality, human welfare, local food, close to city local food sales	Non academic feedback/presentations (games...) Youth engagement: traditional gender roles Encourage young girls. Giving examples, advocate, role models Offering ag science/related options in 2nd level schools Link agricultural/rural to other subjects in school (English/Irish/other) More funding to 'free up' women to demonstrate forms.	using what is already existing...(sources, infrastructure) education – handbooks for kids – stories from the farm education for professionals working the older generation, not only in social care (e.g. wif company), - try to keep people in the community, reuse the building for that...localize services (school care – who brings the child to school etc...) Lack of social capital: Creating aggregation centres to exchange knowledge and skills.
	Inspire – to show up	Libraries Organising cultural events and festivities with a great focus on sustainability
	Collaboration (food network) local markets Fair price to farmers Planning (agri grants like TAMS and planning requirements) Policy: People with knowledge need to be informing policy Policy consultations need to be followed through Women need to share these experiences	Create participatory activities in which people of an area can discuss needs and future visions Create welcoming and integrating facilities for migrants Provide services and jobs (with a great focus on gender) Most issues are localised in the south of Italy where the women at the table come from How to build a network Local workshop
	Accountability – rules/laws	Mentorship to exchange knowledge and social capital
	Accountability – rules/laws	Mentor: women-driven companies -> entrepreneurs
	Planning: Need for flexibility in the planning system. Ireland – Ire 204. Sustainable materials – Romania Need to be more aware to achieve things a holistic way (a vision) Women need to be invited to feed in Local meeting places "pub" supported by community based enterprise funding -> knowledge hub, opportunity hub, rural incubator space Social assistance: a place to go, medical assistance, shelter	Role model Moral support Strengthening each other Community for female rural entrepreneurs Leadership skills Find sustainable way to produce renewable energy considering the welfare of animals and plants
	A house for all generations, coworking, kindergarten, elderly day care. All linked together. All generations receive services and help each other	Focussing on consuming less i.e. one main meal
	From private to community funded	Feminine approach to cocreate and connect and to deep ecology (J.Macy) the council of all beings

1 Local development	2 Sustainable lifestyles	3 Community
	<p>1.Available empty houses in the community 2. Convince the owner to rent the house 3. Project office -> application for RDF, soctfund, private foundation</p> <p>Educational system change in primary school (and in kindergarten), increase social competencies strong NGOs, change of legislation</p> <p>New fields (in meaning of sustainability -> public discussion/networking. E.g. co-existence of people of different age</p>	
	<p>prepare ecodesign (reparable things)</p> <p>education of teachers and parents</p>	
	<p>How to change older people: influence of some people (tv shows, articles, ambassadors, respectable people) punishment; additional costs, taxes etc.</p>	
	<p>people will be renting different houses and facilities according to needs of life period (young families and older people)</p>	
	<p>Intragenerational collaboration and cooperation (sharing knowledge)</p> <p>outdoor activities with community facilities (fitcenter, indoor, outdoor)</p> <p>Need more public transport (not big bus but minivan)</p> <p>more activities in countryside (no need to travel to the city)</p> <p>more expensive parking</p> <p>school bus needed</p> <p>more afternoon activities in schools and community centers for children (travel together)</p> <p>re-use centres, repair centres</p> <p>Car sharing</p> <p>Shared respect and understanding of different challenges in rural areas and cities.</p>	
	<p>Build value chains to support each other and spread products and services</p>	
	<p>IT-infrastructure, internet and cellphone coverage is necessary in the whole country, everywhere (work and run business with less transportation)</p> <p>Help people see "whats in it for me" in a sustainable lifestyle in their context</p> <p>Bring the countryside wisdom into the cities</p> <p>Awareness that every choice makes a difference</p> <p>Create the small solution in electricity and water supply to make sure we have functioning cells even if the bigger system goes down</p> <p>Put solar panels on roofs, above parking lots etc. not on farm land. Develop batteries and storage to further make sharing as needed possible.</p>	

4 Sustainable farming	5 Products and services	6 Concerted action
Give away a seed package to the municipality inhabitants. A company sponsored pallet	Learn best practices from other communities (novel services – differences, innovations)	Get individuals and networks stronger Need to involve young people and activate them, give them opportunity to influence policy
School gardens and growing part of the curriculum	Community link – rural buses, rural area routes	Find experienced individuals in the field
Higher margins for farmers	Mobile businesses: Brining rural area businesses to other communities	Improve the skills of people working in the offices and bring them closer to rural areas
Convince the consumers to choose sustainable products by teaching them about how they are produces	Diversification of strategies to promote rural business development (training and support services)	
Support diversified and small scaled farming	Available funding and supports to promote rural business online (to develop, to expand)	
Focus on quality rather than quantity	Development of virtual reality (VR) experiences to promote rural tourism	
Changing norms and values about sustainable farming. Regenerative and ecological	Shared infrastructure and facilities (co-working spaces)	
Acknowledging multiple ways of operating sustainable farming	Community clinic (supporting business concepts; initial and first steps)	
Regulatory frameworks (today based on large scale farming)	Invest in community electric busses	
Simplify roles for small scales farming	Promote the use of other sustainable transportation (busses, trains, bicycles, walking)	
More distribution channels	Transportation on-demand	
Activities to inspire home growers to scale up	Networks to create new companies and support growth	
Create events and meetings to inspire and share knowledge	Offer subsidized land	
	Train the local community so they can apply for newly created jobs	
	Collaboration between smaller communities to fund infrastructure	
	Collaboration between larger and smaller communities	
	Digital services and infrastructure	
	Supplementation of public transport with private services	
	Organisation of demand analysis for local mobility	
	Adoption of measures to match supply and demand for local mobility services	
	Promotion of sustainable mobility e.g. cycling paths	
	Provision of incentives for using public transport	
	Promotion of sharing economy practices and applications at the local level (e.g. carpooling)	
	Promotion of economic diversification	
	Provision of infrastructure and facilities	
	Provision of innovation services	
	Provision of Capacity building for facilitators	

7 New technology	10 Rural livelihoods	12 Rural image
Any technology that already exists (e.g. AI, GPS...) to develop new opportunities	Support local entrepreneurs – subsidies (e.g. LEADER/CLLD)	Men/farming/identity. Backbone of rural society – traditional, expand the understanding
Communication networks/channels	Co-working space	Rural isn't always agricultural. Championing what we are celebrating today
Robotics machines	Local development strategy – bottom-up vision	Female-led networks/spaces where they can come together e.g. ICA
Customer relationships manager software (CRM)	Political will and motivation – driven by vision	Championing women in alternative avenues. Autonomy to be more than what society depicts rural to be
Training platforms (access); enhance and protect skills	Connect with a person that helps develop the village or the business – a process manager/civil servant/LAG manager	Getting into roles at a local level. Community development – if women aren't at the table change cannot happen. Take no secretary role – lead role. Need for confidence more than competent at being the lead.
Funding availability	Connection – people – local development – political will – keep motivating	Connect people and communities – through foundations for special causes
Clean energies (customised development)	Organize conditions of engagement of rural women in tourism (workshops: education, cooperation): municipalities, LAGs, agencies, TICs -> Networking	Reconnect with place as part of culture, identity, living and value system
Tailored to the local community	Promote rural regions as a pocket of tourist services, destination management	Make possible for external (city) to connect to the villages – place, nature, products, culture
IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) Management	Defend from overtourism -> to direct tourists to other places through stories	Working with pride of identity – proud of youth that stay, pride of heritage without political agenda (has to be inclusive); pride and reconnecting values (finding others)
Great when works but rural areas are still disadvantaged	Keep local festivities	Newcomers in the rural – not farmers, are remote workers move from urban to rural as a lifestyle choice. Need to attract them
Internet connectivity (selective population decline – pre-Covid?)		Myth of rural – rural idyl. Need for place promotion of rural e.g. place for innovation and women innovators
Mobile phone connectivity and networks		Two tier gallery of action – showcase positive and combat negative/protect image
Policy to support community development (rural isolation)		Need to protect rural, its essence, preserve tranquillity. Can't have massive population increase as this would change the rural.
Rural hub – bringing together social interaction		Need for a bottom-up assembly, women as leaders of this. Women can communicate these issues, protect rural and promote image. Women have capacity to do this if given the opportunity
Changing social policy in line with technology developments		Planning of rural village development – in considered/strategic way e.g. deal with dereliction, not just new developments
		Women given opportunity to influence rural planning process
		Time to be involved and influence. Policy to assist tie off.
		Finland example of support for time-off for farmers – extend to maternity leave for farmers. For example in Slovenia there is an extended leave system.
		Political level can do harm to rural image e.g. local-led development can copy ideas from other areas
		Brining an urbanised approach to rural – needs protection from this.
		Laws/rules – focus on collaboration and accountability. Local population responsible for development
		Co-creation of placemaking (e.g. the Netherlands)
		Skills sharing – shared growth

12 Rural Image	12 Rural Image	12 Rural Image
Ireland: Dublin centre. Unbalanced growth (East-West) Need for more soft and hard infrastructure (e.g. childcare), facilities Increased investment in rural areas e.g. services (e.g. police, post offices) Training - invest back in the community	Improve/change marketing narratives More local market places Use existing community spaces for local food marketing Unwell the hidden local knowhow	Visitor tax: appropriate infrastructure, local governance, local benefits Widening the image of rural areas, spread the word of what is actually there Goal: region can produce healthy food choices for population and in doing so create a landscape bringing good life surroundings. Goal: People in the countryside often have knowledge in both new and older ways of doing things and can do things themselves. Value and share that.
Public transport	Social marketing	Goal: Small businesses in rural areas are more self sufficient and contribute to the "biodiversity of economics". The bigger and bigger companies are more globally vulnerable. Government should embrace and support this diversity. Small together is another kind of big.
You need to be strategic Keep/create community spaces Branding of rural areas (image of agriculture) Solidarity	Awareness building Tailored training opportunities Research and communication programs Environmental education	Public communication have to know, see and highlight the contributions of rural areas to society Small contributions from municipality goes a long way in rural collaborations - economically smart use of tax money Do good things and talk about it Changing the story -> values, narratives systems
Policy thinking - switch to bio/regional perspective Partnerships (e.g. CAP, 60+) More and more precise info on packages (origin, environmental footprint)	Tell the story (romantic) Diversification Establish infrastructure	Belonging part -> focus on where people already are, support Life serving -> cultural shift Policy making in less strickter rules/role perspective (not being mother or entrepreneur or employer). Based on practicality. Seasonality.
Expand "farmers markets" practices (online platform for local marketing) Collaborate with schools in a way that children learn where food comes from e.g. visit farms, school gardens Workplace gardens	Look at it as "innovative space". Part of european story. Role for EU- level policy and politics e.g Netherlands forestry activity. New models and practices in nature conservation Highlight different land activities Value	Rethinking how we do policy making: what values are behind? what is the policy making process? what values underpin it? more inclusive. Networks for women in forestry and in hunting - best practices Lectures for women to get more knowledge
Rooftop farms Local farmer sales-marketing cooperatives Customer education (what's local, what's healthy)	Balance interest and demands, value chain. e.g tourism can be positive + negatives -> capacity must be considered Rural areas must be viable and vibrant "part-time living" policy. If paying tax in one place - should contribute to second location	Women only because otherwise women hesitate to talk and contribute Include men in the learning process in order to get a broader perspective and also educate them Role models
Reduce packaging - plastic (you don't need packaging on many products)	Land reform. Commoning and nature restoration: making the countryside and land more accessible. Commoning of land as a strategy to bring people to the rural areas Taxes diversification. Different for different areas based on the amount of services or whether its your 1st or 2nd home	

13 Local food	14 Policy-making	15 Funding models
Develop short to intermediate food supply chains, but there are many obstacles. Need for skills, education of farmers	Training: needs resources for gender specific programmes. Funding. Co-working space. Shifting responsibility from state to organisations, results in not enough core resources. Working with the unknown, when will there be funding available – bringing the responsibility to local people rather than local authority	Innovation grants for women
Expectations – food availability. Value of food needs to increase. Food waste, lost touch with seasons, cheap food	Innovation – taken a different identity due to funding calls – challenges	Top-up wage for women in rural areas, also for business owners
Consumer- farmer - all players in supply chain need education and support	Local development groups are being diminished – human connection	100% grants, no co-financing
Farmer can be seen as victim of food system.	Lack of social capital not really an issue in Irish context	Less bureaucracy, easier access to public funds
Regional players – support e.g. incentives to eat local	Networks that wish to specifically support women in business – listening to the organisations that are listening to the problems on the ground. Where women can find all learning in one place	Start-up funds for services, not just products Worklife balance measures: Public daycare, subsidised, everywhere, Parental leave – mandator parental leave, Meals provided in schools, After school activities, Eldercare everywhere, Farm relief, Domestic relief – local, social entrepreneurs; state contracted; tax deductions, Personal assistance in case of disability, Broadband everywhere
How to influence food prices – whole system	Ensuring there is a link/network between organisations that are going for the same funding calls/needs. Creating a hub	
Peer support and skills to support scale-up, logistical support	Need more human interaction to bring action. Local authorities are removed. More funding for people to work to bring people's ideas to fruition – Fund people	Making initial start difficult e.g. don't own assets, get loan
Re educating, eat local and preserve	Childcare systems – not just a women's issue. Also societal issues – domestic violence	Grant/funding – funds credited after money spend, initial outlay made
Local produce – define and regulate	Can't have a functioning society without appropriate childcare. Knock – on services closing	Need for further training and education in this space
Access to local food – honesty boxes run by women. Also farm shops, erratic availability needs to be addressed	Core funding – extra work – more than just call after call	Example from Sweden/Finland/Nordic countries – try your idea. Educational programme for schools: Could cultivate programme with schools, rural based projects, give grants, build skills of entrepreneurship, transition year opportunities; Get innovators/local rural businesses to speak in schools
Other innovative models e.g. vending machines, cooperatives and partnerships e.g. more appetite for these in beef versus horticulture need change here	Reporting – numerous different agencies – cohesion needed	Mentoring - female founders fund, also available support
Profile of farming is negative, farming is becoming more industrialised	Lack of funding for service providers (e.g. hairdresser, beauticians, shops etc.). They are contributing to rural and forgotten in the process. Remembering them in the funding calls	Use technology – make funding opportunities easier to find. One platform – find all available grants etc
Regional level institutions sourcing local food e.g. schools in Germany	Tick box exercises – supports women make a contribution	Start your own business support – e.g. for self-employed, give supports so not 'on your own', need to be risk taker (professionally and personally), fund to support first year in business.
Depending on product different solutions depending on market e.g. beef into cooperatives because national market. Milk can find local market so there is less need for cooperation	Women hold and contribute significantly to social capital in rural areas. Have ability to bring people together	Agriculture/farming seen as a profession – a career option. Need for a word change not farmer = are 'food producer'. Change of language and perception
Promotion of local food	Local level elections – EU shift, women running for these roles. Need for leadership	Change vision – not only one option
Farm revitalization	Understanding how the system works – what are we doing to support women in politics – need for supports at national level	Top-down policy approach – EU to local. Need for more bottom up. More locally led policy initiatives
shared urban gardens (also in villages)	Support partnership public-private for car sharing	Educate on diversification options – multifunctionality of farming. Have a female founders fund and mentors
Local markets and vending machines	Support woman taxi businesses providing support in admin and taxes while having a % of traffic for community	Online and enjoyable process. Mygov.ie (good example)

13 Local food	14 Policy-making	15 Funding models
Prepayment from customers to food producers	Support development of car share practices: volunteer drivers from local community who take elderly to daily needs, low cost pick-up service for all	Easier for women with a research background. More difficult for communities
Development of cooperatives	Create a special group to work and participate in municipal administration (women)	Triage (in person). To save time for the applicant. Importance of human connection. For example the local enterprise officers (sign-posting position) Triage (online) – you fill in info about your profile and you get the best funding options for you. Website listing specific services and resources and funding and people to contact if you have a business idea and want to develop it.
Subsidies for investments (machines, equipment)	Support financially the peer to peer approach in rural areas	Problem: differences between public funding and EU funding. Dissemination of information. Information is not provided locally
Workshop for gardening knowledge transfer	Reform education system to “teach” long-term achievement	
Building kindergartens and health facilities	Use a social media to catch young peoples attention	Feel that people are actually interested in helping you.
Educational gardens at all levels in school (kindergarten, high school) Create community local events: produce, prepare and enjoy food together at a long table. Pride and inclusion in the community	Invent the cutting of social development skills funds Consider positive externalities generated by some services (e.g public transport) (a shared cost model)	Match funding (issue!) – for people who want to start from scratch and don’t have capital. There is a way to take loans but that can also be problematic. Solution: Microfinancing – linking directly microfinancing with match funding
Localized public procurement	Financing structures have a broader view	Policy makers are faceless. More engagement with users. Make policy makers apply for funding so they understand first hand what the issues are.
Prolonged seasons through new “old” practices Government funding for collaboration, funding for material, equipment to benefit the results Women-initiated CSA Parent community decides where to source products for cafeteria Municipality, community, and private companies take care of the difference that “local menu” creates	Measurements of success in business Change in political framework Incentives to impacts in strengthen ecological and social values Change in ways of talking and measure success	More sharing of ideas (between entrepreneurs, researchers, policy makers). Building on existing idea. Students of MsC in innovation helping out people who have an idea/entrepreneurs to apply for funding. Creating synergies between researchers and entrepreneurs Find the right expertise Inform people about the possibility to be funded (appropriate support)
Education programme to explain why it’s important to eat local. Including local farmers, health professionals, kids, peer to peer	Structures for support of risk and failures	
Multifunctional spaces where municipality owns the space which is then used for: cooking meals for elderly, school meal restaurant, bar and restaurant for community Run by local community women Find a way of distribution: from the farm to customers Educate customers to use local food: promote, excursions, schools, exhibitions		
Improve infrastructure in peripheria areas: transport, broadband, community based sharing machines and equipment		
Cooperate among farmers in selling products, to organize local shops by municipalities Focus on organic farming and sustainable packaging		

16 Heritage	17 Human welfare	18 Nature conservation
Stigma about rural heritage by people living/growing up in cities	Networking events	Women care for life and community
Certification of agri products	Digital detox	Primary needs: water, garden and food
Create pride around cultural heritage/traditional products	Initiative "day without phones"	Need for water to come back to food production
Bigger issue for smaller countries like Ireland	Common events and festivals organized by locals, bottom up	Growing your own food through a community garden
Encourage children to engage in farming (especially women). Farming very much connected to environmental sustainability	Presentation of good practices	Recover forgotten knowledge
Women involved very much in multifunctional farming and encouraging that.	Revitalization of common spaces	Regenerative and permaculture. We as regenerators of ecosystem. Rather than cause deprecation, desertification and ground water pollution.
	Sport activities, workshops (yoga)	Interspecific consciousness -> co-operation between all beings
	Revitalization of local cultural heritage (heritage, customs)	Quote by Einstein: When there wont be bees anymore, in a few years there wont be humans anymore
	Family policies: affordable childcare, parental leaves	
	Basic infrastructure -> transport -> schools	
	Livelihoods	
	Job opportunities	
	Local identities -> heritage -> living traditions, cultural life	
	Local networking (associations, NGOs, LEADER programs, civil dialogue)	
	Awareness of the beauty of rural areas	
	Promotion. Social marketing	
	Sustainable tourism	
	Education	
	Gender equality culture, laws and policies	
	Internet access	
	Holistic approach	
	Nature: Promote outdoor activities, incentives, living in nature	
	Mental health	
	Quality of life	
	Working from home, co-working spaces	
	Transport and connectivity, between cities and rural areas	
	Sense of community	
	Family services	
	Elderly care	

19 New competences	20 Gender roles
Funding to educate and empower rural areas (women)	Policies related to education (from kindergarten to professional position)
Reforming gender roles	We tolerate!!! – we are capable of change but we need to visualise a different role (gender is not only for woman) we should normalize man and women job (man do also another job – care for parents, children)
Where is the power? -> Empower the right entities, people who support sustainability	Freedom of choice – !!! some women like the traditional model....
Media critic -> What kind of reality do we share?	Strong focus on education, training
Sharing and continuing the sustainability wisdom by thinking and way of doing by young people	media advertisement play a significant role...not always realistic, (training for media professionals)
Educational curriculum changes -> more information of gender equality, sustainability etc. Environmental education from early childhood (kindergarten)	be sensitive not to turn off anti-men (not woman only!), gender is for everyone!
More cross field knowledge in curricula	Men need to be involved
New competencies can create new jobs-> green jobs	To avoid Irritation /trigger of „gender“ term
Boost experience learning e.g green kindergarten	More women in various trades
Take advantage of previous knowledge (good practices) and use it in a new context	Encourage, create role models for women in different trades
New educational forms, interdisciplinary connections	Expand role models for men as well (male nurses, caring roles)
hands-on approach, practical knowledge	Break old role models for both men and women
Young people involvement	Design machines and products that fit to women's body/hands (tractors, gadgets)
Opportunities	Equal parental leave rules
	Equal representation in decision making (like national agricultural planning and strategies)
	Improve availability of childcare services in rural areas
	Improve remote working conditions (internet infrastructure)
	Work place could have children's room and playground
	Spaces for children should be supported by government (subsidies)
	Improve work-life balance
	Same opportunities for boys and girls
	More funding steered towards women
	Semantic wording, Not only technology, innovation and economic growth
	Moral support
	Empowerment
	Cultural change is difficult and takes time
	Mutual support and equal decision making
	Difficult to find measures to impact the issue
	Role of media influencing gender attitudes
	Different spaces need addressing e.g. domestic company boards
	Need gender balanced approach in different spaces

Annex 3. Vision workshop output translated into primitive scenario cards.

SCENARIO CARD
SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES

VISION 2040: Sustainable lifestyles have been adopted in a way that adds possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Community funded facilities and services
- Intergenerational housing models
- More sustainability and social competencies in various curricula
- Local hubs
- Promotion of NGOs for sustainability
- Intergenerational knowledge sharing
- Maintenance of local services to avoid travelling
- Circular economy practices: re-use, repair, recycle
- Sharing economy practices
- Promotion of sustainable lifestyle models

SCENARIO CARD

COMMUNALITY

VISION 2040: Communality has been organised in a way that adds possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Creation of aggregation centres to exchange knowledge and skills and enhance social capital
- Libraries as accessible locations of knowledge and communality
- Organisation of sustainability oriented cultural events and festivities
- Organisation of local futures workshops to co-create common visions
- Creation of welcoming and integration facilities for migrants
- Provision of services and jobs with a focus on gender
- Adoption of place-based policies

SCENARIO CARD

SUSTAINABLE FARMING

VISION 2040: Promotion of sustainable farming that add possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- School gardens as a growing part of the curriculum
- Promotion of sustainable consumer choices
- Support for diversified and small scale farming
- Changing norms and values for sustainable, regenerative and ecological farming
- Acknowledging multiple ways to sustainability
- Transformation of regulatory framework (currently based on large scale farming)
- Simplification of rules for small scale farming
- More distribution channels
- Activities to inspire home growers to scale up
- Events and meetings to inspire and share knowledge

SCENARIO CARD

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

VISION 2040: Provision of products and services that add possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Supplementation of public transport with private services
- Organisation of demand analysis of local mobility
- Adoption of measures to match supply and demand for local mobility services
- Promotion of sustainable mobility, e.g. cycling paths
- Provision of incentives for using public transport
- Promoteion of sharing economy practices and applications at the local level (e.g. carpooling)
- Promotion of economic diversification
- Provision of infrastructure and facilities
- Provision of innovation services
- Provision of capacity building for facilitators

SCENARIO CARD

NEW TECHNOLOGY

VISION 2040: New technology has been developed and used in a way that add possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Access to training platforms enhances and protects skills
- Availability of funding
- Clean energy (customised development)
- Tailored to the local community
- IPR management (Intellectual Property Rights)
- Any technology that already exists (e.g. AI, GPS) to develop opportunities
- Communication networks and channels
- Robotics machines

SCENARIO CARD

RURAL IMAGE

VISION 2040: Rural image has been renewed in a way that adds possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Diversification of rural image (not only agriculture)
- Championing women and supporting alternative avenues
- Pride of being rural: identity, culture, values, places
- Place-based policies: strategic, local-led, collaborative, sustainable in local context
- Avoiding urban bias: sovereign rural worldview
- Necessary local basic services and infrastructure
- Open community spaces open also for newcomers
- Place branding and information about the origin of food, energy and products

SCENARIO CARD

LOCAL FOOD

VISION 2040: Local food has mainstreamed in a way that adds possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Promotion of local food through education and funding
- Revitalisation of traditional practices
- Community supported agriculture
- Local logistic systems
- Development of local cooperatives
- Educational farms and gardens for all ages
- Communal food events
- Localised public procurement

SCENARIO CARD

POLICY MAKING

VISION 2040: Policy making has been reformed in a way that adds possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Support for public-private partnerships
- Support for new models in local logistics
- Support for local volunteering
- Support for peer to peer practices in rural areas
- Better possibilities for women to contribute to local democracy and administration

SCENARIO CARD

FUNDING MODELS

VISION 2040: Novel funding models have been adopted that add possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Innovation grants
- Better support for starting from scratch
- Easy access to funding
- Funding information and education
- Mentors in funding
- Vision based funding
- Funds for locally led policy initiatives
- Matching platforms: funders and innovators
- Locally engaged policy makers

SCENARIO CARD

HUMAN WELFARE

VISION 2040: Promotion of human welfare that add possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Holistic approach
- Nature: promotion and incentives for outdoor activities, living in nature
- Support for diversified and small scale farming
- Changing norms and values for sustainable, regenerative and ecological farming
- Acknowledging multiple ways to sustainability
- Transformation of regulatory framework (currently based on large scale farming)
- Simplification of rules for small scale farming
- More distribution channels
- Activities to inspire home growers to scale up
- Events and meetings to inspire and share

SCENARIO CARD

NEW COMPETENCES

VISION 2040: Provision of new competences that add possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Provision of funding to educate rural women
- Removal of gender-based constraints in all kind of education
- Empowerment of sustainability agency
- Reduction of media's influence and stereotypes on one's own choices in e.g. education and career
- Promotion of sustainability wisdom
- Promotion of education on sustainability and gender equality
- Provision of interdisciplinary education
- Provision of competences needed in green jobs
- Promotion of experience learning

SCENARIO CARD

GENDER ROLES

VISION 2040: Gender roles have been reformed in a way that adds possibilities for women-led sustainability innovations in rural areas.

INGREDIENTS (FOR EXAMPLE):

- Equal educational opportunities for all
- Freedom of choice for all
- Acceptance and tolerance
- Diverse role models
- Equal parental leave rules
- Equal representation in decision making
- Childcare services and communal spaces for children in rural areas
- Improvement of work-life balance

Annex 4. Output of the scenario workshops ('oldies).

2 Sustainable lifestyles	3 Community	5 Products and services
Sustainable rural transportation is in place and other infrastructure (broadband, social services e.g. health, childcare) in rural areas. Community centres, sports and cultural infrastructure	Building bridges <= Hampered by social media bubble	'Uber system' for local public goods
Local hubs (integrated - services and infrastructure)	Common factor, speak common language, 'undercover'	Subsidised (?) taxi for rural areas
Newcomers versus existing population	Sense on communality, belonging	Have somewhere to eat, to dance, to go out
Rural areas often more traditional and gender roles must change. Sharing tasks in rural areas beyond traditional roles. Cultural change.	Newcomers acceptance - Individualisation of new rural	Women innovators and their encouragement
Inclusion of men in discussion on task burden takes cultural change	Physican infrastructure <= Offered by municipality	Apps for carpool groups
More local, autonomous practice of re-use, repair, recycle. Community scale	Committed and motivated people	Lack of transport: networking, market access, sustainability, unsafe at roads
Often one person is needed to organise a community (newcomer, return migrant). Also followers. How do you support these? Visioning. Need for trust, bring together capacity, common belonging	Recognition of women's visions	=> See that public transport is a public good - connection to local and national policy makers and politicians
Recognise, reward and acknowledge innovative step-takers.	'Entrepreneurship feeling'	=> Create biking paths and walking paths: physical exercise, make children more independent, less pollution
The option to assess over one name to own land and farm, with explicit consent.	Cusiosity, 'Mediterranean mindset', hospitality	=> Create more use of public transportation: extra advantages for using public transportation
	Tacit knowledge of culture, 'unwritten codes'	Local link in Ireland is a good example (public good, economically not viable)
	Physical infrastructure => Childcare facilities, senior centres, markets	Organise circular economy for local transport: how to convince politicians for investing in public goods
	Tourism routes, stops for locals - women walks - Program incentivising landowners and farmers to host	Ask what people want

2 Sustainable lifestyles	3 Community	5 Products and services
	More people or people moving back to rural areas is needed	Women more included in choices regarding tourism, parks etc.
	=> How can their inclusion be supported	Level 1: Help for entrepreneurs
	=> Places need to be more attractive	Level 2: Help for the people around
	=> Change narratives (no more: 'no services', 'no people')	Emotional return home
	=> Creating welcoming interaction facilities for migrants and other newcomers	=> Women who are migrant care professionals return to rural communities
	=> Combine 'parliament' and cultural event, e.g. 'Green night'	=> They become social entrepreneurs providing care services locally in PP-partnership
	=> Event is the end of a long process and ongoing discussion - work is done in the villages	=> Knowledge transfer and exchange
	=> Common conclusion is reached in the end and rooted in the local context	=> More women innovators
	=> Learn from others, sharing experiences of different actors in the area	=> Integration of migrant women
	=> Leading to common manifesto that everyone agrees upon	=> Free more women from care duties
	Rural areas having clear vision based on their areas: cultural heritage, environment etc. that is communicated outside	=> Better care locally
	=> How to create vision that provides new narratives	=> Improved infrastructure and services
	Hosting outside volunteers and other visitors to bring new ideas and 'ask stupid questions'	
	=> Rural areas can be other than just farming etc., why not come to rural village to study	
	How to involve policy makers	
	=> Showing through communal activity that it makes sense to invest and support the rural areas	
	=> These needs to be something existing based in community	
	=> Be part of the decision-making: getting involved in the politics, at least in the local level	
	=> Involve policy-makers so that they understand local context	
	Community needs to be reframed as 'official' vs. associations, policies: just 'the spark' is not enough	

12 Rural image	13 Local food	14 Policy-making
Organising capacity building activities for local and regional authorities, official, general public about reproducing stereotypes by local action groups (LAGs) together with researchers.	Children – school public kitchen, education (all types of farming), organic school garden, part of the curriculum, onsite growing/veg and use the food in the school, free school lunches	Volunteer work supporting local social services as a kind of extra social infrastructure but forms a paid job for volunteering people
Building pride through community spaces online to engage with society via campaigns to support all emerging groups.	Experimental learning	Regional development planning is relying on additional social service from semi-official volunteer - not work (which don't decrease public social work investment)
Allocation of already available government funding to spotlight alternative lifestyles in rural area.	Cycle of life approach	There is quota system in local social work planning boards to secure fair utilisation of volunteer work (especially of women)
Municipalities have a responsibility to support and get funding for it.	Technology as an enabler, using social media	With quota system it becomes custom to have balanced gender structure
Leverage technologies to connect rural innovators with local markets, investors and knowledge-sharing platforms.	Local food for use at local level - Local database (e.g. app in Sweden and Slovenia) technology to enable local suppliers connect with customer base; Regional level – drive for food produced locally. Short food supply chain (but seasonality is an issue e.g. Sweden very seasonal); Government initiatives and supports (grant aid); Community connectivity, accessibility; Variety and availability across the seasons; fair price for the farmer; funding (from EU and government, access to finance to invest in innovation-technology; funding provided by and at local level); cooperatives	Peer to peer support, role models valued
Rewrite school textbooks & adjust curricula to present diverse rural lifestyles to students younger generations. Through demanding the ministry of education to reconsider the stereotyping of rural life in education.	Cultural shift and mindset to achieve this vision – Go back to promoting traditional practices; new practices via technology; emotional/personal attachment to food (domestic and community practices); e.g. pickled vegetables; history and evolution of the 'plant-seed'	Gender quotas and financial support for volunteer work should be (will be – is) written in law so that changes of government do not change or benefit quotas or volunteer work
	Legislation – security to producers, health and wellbeing, environment-food management-technology, food quality, traceability, biowaste. Need for mandate e.g. Dig for Victory campaign	EU level is overseeing national implementation of laws and policies

12 Rural image	13 Local food	14 Policy-making
	Why we need legislation – need governance e.g. blueberries being imported because it is cheaper. Need ways to implement/include local food in the system	Gender balancing policies begins from education and raising boys and girls to new kinds of balanced gender roles in society
	Circular economy e.g. local compost	Research is supporting balancing gender gap should be (is) supported
	Novel untapped initiatives are needed e.g. community supported agriculture, urban agriculture, access to land (use/rent/ownership)	Step by step balanced gender participation in all sectors of society, from family cars to technology development has become new normal
	Farmer viewed and valued as a profession, break the stigma. The farmer – new type of 'farmer', part-time farmer/veg box farmer.	The role of social media: mindset change is infiltrated
	Need shift in education of farming – new way of life, entrepreneurship; additional skills to support part time farmers (e.g. farmers and ski instructor, example discussed from Lyon)	Where we influence: we offer our insights in 'man' conferences
		We need laws and rules about participation, what can't be changed after elections
		Education in primary school for young kids. There are politicians and entrepreneurs and employed people and train the trainers. Roles woman/man national programs
		Research, need to be in ... [unfinished sentence...]
		The products need to be good. Women can support other women more
		Local cooperatives: shared responsibility
		Social infrastructure/development support local volunteers is a paid job in regional planning
		Financial support for a role model
		How does a day of the volunteer support look like. Volunteer supporter needs to be in the democracy system
		Ideal situation is that men feel responsible for the family as well.
		Mentoring: peer to peer
		Food: where does the food come from? Celebrate the food, local food, fair price for farmers. Technology and apps support where you can find 'markets'. Community supported agriculture. Farmer is valued.
		Supporting remote working
		Local hubs for care, transport, social services are in an integrated approach.
		IT systems: The citizens are the owners of the data (not that we have to pay companies for it). It is in the collective/cooperatives, less transport because of combinations.

15 Funding models	19 New competences	20 Gender roles
Key issue is lack of novel funding models.	Informal intergenerational childcare/hobbies: example organise table tennis after school by retired people (very popular)	Tradition: culture - family. Equal understanding of gender in positive sense, at all ages
-For smaller innovators/farms: more funding through LEADER & CAP. Grants for smaller start ups that don't need scaling	Missing a pool or talent <=> not being asked	Equity: based society, intersectional frameworks, different types of women. Change power structures
Micro grants and credits	Regulations are difficult => no overregulation	Access to opportunities: link education and infrastructure. Funding and government structure. Tackle issues: domestic violence. Community based insight
mentor connected to help in applying	Help youngsters to increase their self-esteem - Get them out of their mobile phones and 'own' bubble	Economic independence: Promote occupations that are not usual e.g. women engineers. Promote both ways. Equal parental leave. -Local system: navigating national system promotion of what exists -Different understandings: establish clarification, common understanding, core understanding -Current discourses: Italian laws of "gender ideology". Political backlash.
Post-application beyond funding models and using funding "smart" utilization of funding (social capital aspect)	Community ambassadors to facilitate this	What do rural women want: Voice of women need to be heard
Flexible and simplified funding and granting process	Interdisciplinary education	Value and care more: No financial value associated. Negative discourse (suicide) Age discrimination in work life.
National strategic plans CAP. Agri side is lacking so we lose smaller innovations and farms	Microlearning to boost diverse competences	Protecting gender dimension and balance: gender proofing. Care for elderly.

15 Funding models	19 New competences	20 Gender roles
Matchmaking service/meeting. Create a national platform that you can find all sources of info and funding.	Trainings on rural entrepreneurship	Proper funding is in place by 2040
No need for match funding. Have community based funding which is also community decision based (co-op funding) . Funding through community rather than direct to the project (a collective decision)	Short regional workshops	Clarification campaign established: Shared understanding on how to communicate
Multisector funding. A funding pot with ingredients for ideas, no matter where or what sector. Create a platform and funding programme (multi-actor review process)	Benchmarking with women on entrepreneurship	Stakeholders agree on shared vision on all levels.
	Removal of gender-based constraints in all kind of education	Safehabitus: EU project exploring these themes.
	360° media campaigns to raise awareness included in education system	
	Women's community of empowerment	
	New competences involving Artificial Intelligence	

Annex 5. FLIARA policy scenarios, extensive versions.

1

Valued and Visible: Empowering Rural and Farm Women as Change Makers

Problems and drivers

Many rural areas suffer from a lack of social capital due to outmigration and economic decline. Lack of faith in the future leads to passivity, deficit of involvement and an absence of investments for the future both in agriculture and rural economies. In many instances, deeply rooted thought patterns and behaviours, prevaills, including harmful consumption patterns. Rural and farm women, if fully acknowledged, supported and connected for their work can disrupt these cycles, fostering more sustainable, inclusive and future-oriented rural systems.

Policies and pathways

Capacity building policies, such as coaching initiatives and entrepreneurial competence programmes strengthen social capital and expand networks essential for driving change and exploiting opportunities. **Visibility platforms**, including awards and media exposure help elevate female role models, transforming the invisible into visible and providing positive reinforcement to pioneering women. In all societal systems, path dependency often hinders change. To counter this, focused **incentives** are essential to support female change makers in delivering innovations that promote multidimensional sustainability. This requires a **holistic policy paradigm**, one that integrates social, environmental, economic and cultural dimensions rather than focusing on a single aspect. Finally, **anti-discrimination policies** addressing gender, age and geographical disparities are critical to ensuring that existing potential for sustainability transformation is not lost or overlooked in society.

Outcomes

Valued, visible and empowered women deliver transformative sustainability innovations and cluster change agents. Positive future perspectives and visions have become more common, leading to an increase in investments for the future. Concerted actions toward sustainable futures have taken root in many regions. This has added sustainability and resilience in agriculture and rural areas.

SCENARIOS

Diversified Rural Images beyond Agriculture and Traditional Norms

2

Problems and drivers

Many rural regions suffer from limited economic diversification and a widespread lack of sustainability knowledge, both inside and outside their rural communities. These issues are particularly acute in remote rural areas which often face selective population decline as young, educated and especially women leave in search of better opportunities elsewhere. The decline is reinforced by several forces that maintain path dependency in thought and action: peer pressure, compromised public policies, rigid traditions and persistent gender stereotypes. Collectively, these factors limit innovation and adaptability in rural areas. Moreover, rural communities are often shaped by an urban-centric lens in how they are viewed and valued. This in turn contributes to poor communication and marketing of local strengths and opportunities further weakening the prospects for rural regeneration and sustainability.

Policies and pathways

Change becomes possible only when positive agricultural and rural realities and opportunities are made visible and accessible. This is achieved through several measures. **Collaboration with creative and culture industries** helps reshape a new image in various media platforms as well as artistic and cultural stages. Educational reforms, such as **updating school textbooks and curricula** introduces young people to the diversity of rural lifestyles beyond traditional farming, showcasing new employment opportunities (including remote work) and sustainable farming practices, such as agroecology. These efforts help shift perceptions and inspire a new generation. At the same time, key enablers, including, farm advisors, administrators, financiers and policy makers are educated and empowered to **support a broader, more inclusive vision of the rural future** through their own work. Importantly, top-down, uniform policies are replaced by place-based policies to allow exploitation of all local resources for sustainable rural futures and to allow communities to take pride in shaping their own future pathway.

Outcomes

Old-fashioned and male-dominated mindsets and stereotypes within and outside agriculture and rural communities have become updated. The new public image of agriculture and rural areas has attracted newcomers and encouraged existing actors – especially women – to step into roles once deemed off-limits. As a consequence, agricultural and rural realities have diversified and provided new inputs for positive communication, self-esteem and pride. Attractiveness of agriculture and rural areas has increased among young, educated and women.

Sustainable Agriculture: A Positive and Empowering Choice for Women

3

Problems and drivers

Farmers have become a minority in modern societies and urbanisation has led to a growing disconnect between people and food production. Farming itself suffers from several sustainability problems, namely, a dependence on fossil inputs, soil degradation, water management, loss of all kinds of diversity (actors, practices, products, biodiversity) and unjust distribution of value added in the food chain. A lack of young farmers is an increasing threat to food security and public goods delivered by farming. Farmers preferring small-scale, nature-oriented or social farming (e.g. women, young, value-driven farmers) are not served by agricultural policies that are targeted for large, specialised volumes.

Policies and pathways

For agriculture to be truly attractive option for women, it should offer diverse and profitable pathways that align with their skills, values and aspirations. **Information campaigns** have brought about a cultural shift and mindset that grants more value to environmental, social and cultural aspects beyond cheap food paradigm. **Revise and update regulatory and governance frameworks**, which currently favour large scale farming operations, is essential to lower the entry barriers for women and young farmers, allowing upscaling and multiple ways of operating sustainable farms. **Reforming agricultural education** incorporating school gardens, educational farms and local food events etc. contributes to a cultural shift in favour of diversification and encourage home growers to expand their activities. As most of the current distribution channels are designed for the low-cost, mass-produced food, **new distribution channels** are established – with dedicated policy support for local, artisan and agroecological producers. These channels prioritise food that offers a fair price for the farmer and focuses on quality rather than quantity. Finally, **consumer enlightenment campaigns** inform consumers about the benefits of diversified food system.

Outcomes

As many women farmers are interested in multidimensional sustainability, the reform has made agriculture a more attractive and accessible choice for women as well. As a consequence, multidimensional sustainability and resilience of agriculture and the food system has made progress on many fronts: informed consumer choices, home gardens, diversity-oriented policies, a rich set of farming styles and distribution channels and increased contributions to the vitality of rural areas. Farming has become a valued profession among all ages, genders and societal groups.

From Margins to Mainstream: Women at the Heart of Sustainable Rural Economies

4

Problems and drivers

Many rural economies are dominated by specialised agriculture and lack of economic diversification within and beyond farming. Urbanisation and concentration tendencies have left rural areas without adequate infrastructure, facilities and public transport. Selective population decline (young, educated, women) has been going on for decades in many rural societies. Consequently, local cultures and traditions marginalise.

Policies and pathways

A **'think small' approach** is the key to local rural communities and economies where scale is important and aligns with local needs and realities. Especially women benefit from **support that is tailored to the community needs** in terms of e.g. advisory services, development projects, business models and fast and micro funding. Granting more autonomy to small-scale, local actors not only improves **local services and infrastructure** that form a precondition to female-led rural innovations but also allows these areas themselves to become targets of innovation. For example, farm-based or co-operative kindergartens, eldercare and social services are emerging as creative, community-driven solutions that both support and are led by women in rural areas. Consequently, positive spirals in local development begin to emerge. Through well-designed national and regional policies, availability of **quality and resilient jobs** is ensured, helping to attract skilled women to rural employment opportunities. **Incentives** for reforming the rural economy at the local level is augmented to promote entrepreneurship and sustainability innovations. At the same time, **welcoming policies** help integrate newcomers into local communities and businesses, contributing to vibrant and resilient rural economies.

Outcomes

More attractive jobs for women have materialised in the rural areas and this has diversified local rural economies. Both increased levels of economic activity and female-led innovations in local infrastructure, logistics and services have increased vitality of rural communities.

Support for Women as Promoters of Sustainable Rural Communities

5

Problems and drivers

Many rural communities fall behind in sustainability and resilience due to lack of social capital, selective population decline, limited availability of feasible housing, lack of involvement, marginalisation of local culture, traditions and community identity as well as ignorance of aesthetic aspects. Weak advocacy and involvement of young people is typical for all kinds of regions, leaving 'alternative' futures out of scope, all of which hinder women's ability to settle and build sustainable lives in rural regions.

Policies and pathways

Sustainable rural communities are ultimately based on institutionalised **place-based, bottom-up policies** manifesting local paradigm. The communities thrive through self-organise systems that mobilise local resources to meet the local needs, something that cannot be achieved through external governance. Self-organisation is based on motivated individuals, particularly women, who often take on central roles in community resilience and innovation. Renewal and continuity are important for the future, so many regions have developed diverse **gateways to local communities** for newcomers and migrants, helping to integrate them into local life and creating new energy within rural systems. A growing wave of **social innovations**, such as pop-up supplies, green care, social farming, co-operative kindergartens, sharing, circular systems offer inclusive models that are especially accessible to women, young people and new residents. These initiatives provide both practice services and economic opportunities, while also empowering women to actively shape and maintain local infrastructure and services. **Resourced local action** reproduces local culture and heritage as well as enhances identity, pride, social capital, concerted action and attractiveness of rural places.

Outcomes

Increased social capital and amplified concerted action in many rural locations have rewritten rural futures with positive stories of success, self-esteem and sustainability. Young people and newcomers have contributed to social innovations that have turned rural communities into attractive, modern and vibrant places to live.

Inclusion and Representation of Agriculture and Rural Women in Networks and Decision-making Forums

6

Problems and drivers

Many networks and decision-making forums continue to lack female representation. This excludes some important perspectives, particularly in the areas of sustainability knowledge, social inclusion and gender specific concerns. This lack of inclusion leads to disengagement, as women see no vision for meaningful contribution, which in turn reinforces a negative cycle of underrepresentation and disinterest.

Policies and pathways

A dual approach is adopted with 'hard' and 'soft' measures implemented to promote gender equality. On the hard side, **National equality laws** prohibiting discrimination (e.g. based on pregnancy and family responsibilities) and promoting gender equality (e.g. mandatory gender equality plans, 40% gender quotas in non-elected governmental and municipal bodies) provide a strong legal foundation. This approach, proven effective in the Nordic countries, helps establish a baseline that will change mindsets, institutionalise equality and encourage female participation across the society. On the soft track, the 'new normal' in society embraces inclusivity across all jobs and positions, meaning that opportunities are **open to all competent people**. The equality principle (act) will be institutionalised through legislation, enhancing **visibility policies** showcasing the benefits of gender equality, namely novel sustainability innovations and the elimination of idea monocultures, and the strengthening of social capital.

Outcomes

Increased inclusion and representation of agriculture and rural women in decision-making forums has enhanced societal performance by fully leveraging the potential of all citizens. This shift has advanced multidimensional sustainability in both agriculture and rural domains.

FLARA

7

Development and Adoption of New Technologies to Improve Farm and Rural Women's Work Life Opportunities

SCENARIOS

Problems and drivers

Many farms and rural communities still lack adequate technologies to exploit work life opportunities, particularly for women engaged in farming and rural enterprise. This technological gap limits productivity, increases the physical burden of work and hinders work life balance between livelihood and personal life for rural and farm women. Defective and outdated technologies reduce desirability of farm jobs and rural life, especially for younger women, leading to a declining interest in farming a viable livelihood. As a result, rural areas face selective population decline, a lack of successors, especially females and a deterioration of social capital and economic capital required for a vibrant rural life.

Policies and pathways

A wide range of technologies exist that can enhance productivity, reduce physical strain and release time for private life. For that end, technologies that are accessible for women are developed for improvement of working on the farm, management of farms and organisation of private and social life. Even more important is targeted **training and education** to ensure women can adopt and benefit from these new technologies. Local Action Groups (LAGs) can serve as effective platforms for such training due to their rural proximity, community involvement and local knowledge. In addition, Fabrication Laboratories (Fab Labs) provide access to learning and collaborating around technologies as also diverse incubators, hubs, innovation forums, machine rings etc. **Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)** play a key role both in developing accessible technologies for women as well as in training women in the utilisation of new technologies. Active inclusion and representation of women within AKIS is adopted both in the coordination bodies and in advisory roles.

Outcomes

Making technology development and training sensitive to gender improves its applicability with many subsequent benefits. Technology-assisted work, management and communication practices have increased productivity, increased attractiveness of farm and rural jobs and improved work life balance especially among farm and rural women.

Accessible and Flexible Funding and Support Models that Enable Diverse Women-led Innovation Journeys in Farms and Rural Areas

8

Problems and drivers

From a gender perspective, many policies are inefficient, distant and/or too bureaucratic to make a change. Poorly designed policies have, in part, contributed to the lack of diversification and social capital in farming and rural communities.

Policies and pathways

Innovation journeys by farm and rural women are diversified and policies designed to mainstream activities don't always align with women's needs. Funding and support models are flexible, allowing a start from the scratch, small business with limited capital, but supporting **scaling up** and growth. More of the funding is **vision based lump sum funding** where funding is not granted for pre-specified measures (person-month based salaries, travel, reports, meetings) but for realising a vision through micro grants and credits. Farm funding policies, *à la* Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), have been adapted to support small innovations. Further on, **funding laboratories, mentorships, innovations hubs, pilot studies and benchmarking** – supported by public funds – provide ideas, assessments and support for female innovators. **Community-based funding** with autonomic community decision making serves the local needs. **Self-sustaining funds** provide low-interest loans for setting up own business.

Outcomes

Unproductive policies have been transformed to observe gender specific aspects. Agriculture and rural economies have diversified allowing full exploitation of local resources and opportunities. Sustainability and resilience of farming and rural communities has improved.

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